

Building a bigger tent: institutional tracking of data publications and maximally FAIR data require rigorous repository metadata standards

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Best practices around management and sharing of research data are rooted in the FAIR Principles. Translating these principles into practice is often challenging, in part because their necessarily high-level framework allows claims of FAIR data when only minimum standards are met (e.g., a dataset having a DOI). Viewing FAIR as a gradient (FAIRness) rather than as a binary requires both greater commitment to the quality of metadata and data and more expansive concepts of what data access and reuse may look like. Most current efforts around improving the FAIRness of data focus the specific use case of data generated by a researcher that is reused for further research by another researcher. However, other entities in the scholarly ecosystem have a vested interest in research data and represent alternative use case. For example, funders are interested in monitoring compliance with data sharing mandates, and research institutions are interested in communicating the full scope of research outputs. Both use cases require the ability to systematically discover datasets at scales much larger than individual researchers through centralized metadata locations (e.g., the DataCite API) and thus rely on quality metadata to discover data. Quality metadata in turn hinge on repository infrastructure and workflows. I will discuss work at the University of Texas at Austin to discover affiliated research datasets and will demonstrate how widespread heterogeneity in repository metadata practices produce extensive gaps in findability. I will then highlight actionable steps that repositories can take to increase dataset FAIRness for non-researcher use cases.

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